

Milestone 3.1: Report on Joint D5-1 / D5-2 Natural Capital Stakeholder Workshop – 19th May 2023

Project D5-1 Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital valuation: Engagement workshop with stakeholder experts to discuss values of forest natural capital and gaps in implementing values and valuation methods

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Summary

This report summarises ideas discussed during a workshop jointly organised between the project RESAS JHI D5-1, *Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital Valuation* and the project RESAS JHI D5-2, *Climate change impacts on Natural Capital*, to explore forest and woodland values and valuation, and risk perceptions of climate change and its impacts on natural capital. After a general introduction of the two projects, stakeholders were split according to their will and interest into two groups, one discussing valuation, the other climate change risk and mitigation strategies. The two breakout sessions were facilitated using a virtual board for participants to report their ideas as single keywords, messages, etc., that were discussed and commented upon following some prompts prepared by the facilitators before the meeting. This report refers to emerging common values in the forest and woodland context, gaps in valuation and opportunities to implement valuation approaches considering the impacts of climate change.

Main findings reveal a limited integration in practice of cultural values, indicating indirectly a higher influence on decision-making from the analysis of those ecosystem services that generate direct monetary benefits. Notwithstanding the absence or limited capacity to encapsulate communities' perspectives in the valuation process and decision-making by eliciting preferences for sense of place and more broadly cultural identity, we positively observed that the forestry industry is ready to implement plans that are not only based on the mere value of timber but consider multiple functionalities of forest in order to respond to the effects of climate change. In addition, it emerged more than once that the valuation process is characterised by a nature of duality, where values can be assigned as a result of either personal or professional interests. Between the two dimensions it is possible to see the generation of feedback loops, wherein the values constructed in one realm influence those constructed in the other, and vice-versa. This dichotomy can generate frustrations because personal and professional values do not always match up and can result in some values (often economic or policy-led) being valued more highly than others. Addressing this dichotomy is not a common practice, research tending to favour communal over subjective values. Implementing a valuation framework that fill these gaps can be a relevant direction for our future research and for practice to facilitate shaping policies that reflect and retain local values in decision-making.

Key Messages:

Key messages that emerged showed the need to:

1. Improve the role of valuation by incorporating cultural aspects related to landscape amenities, cultural heritage and any aspects related to the human and social domain and forest capital in decision-making to balanced out the greater importance given too frequently to monetary values.
2. Consider community views through a collaborative, participatory co-designed approach in the process of informing landscape regional land use policies and plans by capturing the values above-mentioned.
3. Delineate the importance of subjective values beyond communal ones, capturing the dichotomy between personalism and professionalism.
4. Address economic aspects of forestry to build a more resilient industry in the next 50 years, that can consider multiple values such as biodiversity, but that encompasses the role of those species that may easily respond to the effect of climate change.

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D5-1 Joint Natural Capital Workshop with D5-2.

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Introduction

On 19th May 2023 the James Hutton Institute held an **online joint workshop** to gather data for the RESAS projects *JHI D5-1 Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital Valuation* and *JHI D5-2 Climate change impacts on Natural Capital*.

The purpose of the workshop was to listen to and gather a range of expert and stakeholder views on the value of forests and forest natural capital, and perceptions of risks for natural capital under climate change. This document primarily reports the considerations that emerged in the breakout session discussing the role of values and valuation in the forest context (as relating mainly to project D5-1) with the goal of depicting relevant gaps in this field and complementing previous findings from a literature review conducted by the D5-1 research team. It describes the workshop method and results before moving on to a discussion and exploration of limitations and recommendations for future research.

To place the research in context, the Scottish Government's (SG) aspiration is to increase the contribution of natural capital (NC) to a broader range of economic and social benefits. This target is embedded in policies, including the Land Use (LU) Strategy (2021) (Scottish Government, 2021) and Scotland's Forestry Strategy 2019 (Scottish Government, 2019). Policy responses to climate change (CC) and biodiversity crises drive the development towards changes in economic priority areas, with NC becoming the core of Green Recovery. The Dasgupta Report (2021) stresses that humanity underestimates the value of nature leading to overconsumption of natural assets. It promotes NC accounting as a necessary move towards the creation of inclusive wealth accounts which are proposed as new measures of economic progress¹ that account for the benefits from investing in natural assets^[2] more appropriately than GDP.

The D5-1 project aims to build upon current concepts and approaches to advance knowledge and support decision-makers in the wider and more efficient use of natural capital valuation techniques and their combination. We will elaborate a joined-up, systematic theoretical framework that will capture (and help operationalise) multiple values of natural capital. The aim of the workshop was to feed into the wider project by gathering data to inform the framework design.

The workshop was facilitated by Sam Poskitt, Simone Martino and Katy Joyce, and lasted for 2 hours, from 9am to 11am, on 19th May 2023. The event was able to engage in total 27 stakeholders, 17 external and 10 internal from the D5-1 and D5-2 James Hutton Institute research teams. The institutions participating included: *Scottish Government, Cairngorms NP, Scottish Forestry, Forestry and Land Scotland, Forest Research, SEPA, National Farmers Union of Scotland, NatureScot, Scottish Rural Action, South of Scotland Enterprise, Glengarry, Scottish Wildlife Trust, and The James Hutton Institute*. Names of stakeholders are not reported, and information provided in this report is unidentifiable to any specific institution or individual according to the consent form (Appendix I).

This report is a Milestone for the Strategic Research Programme project 'Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation' (JHI-D5-1).

Further details and outputs from the project are available here:

<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/bringing-participatory-approaches-widen-scope-natural-capital-valuation>

¹ this is the sum of accounting values of produced capital, human capital, and NC [2]

Natural Capital Valuation

Method

The workshop was held online to allow for the participation of a range of expert stakeholder participants who may otherwise not have been able to attend. Technological challenges can cause issues within online workshops (and indeed one participant was unfortunately unable to join the workshop due to technical issues but was offered the chance to contribute at a later date), while some critics suggest they may not offer the same level of opportunity as face-to-face interactions to develop the rapport or opportunities for empathic connection required for qualitative data collection (Carter et. al., 2021; Santana et al., 2021). However, in this case the data required was not personal in nature and did not require the development of deeper personal relationships between researcher and participants. Furthermore, while online qualitative research is held at times to exacerbate issues around inclusion this is not the case for the engagement of professional stakeholders and the benefits of online qualitative research for encouraging participation are also espoused (Seymour, 2001). A decision was made, therefore, that due to budgetary and time restraints an online workshop would suffice to offer the best chance of collecting the data we required.

Microsoft Teams was chosen as the platform due to its greater facility to record and transcribe breakout rooms and its greater acceptance amongst professional organisations than JHI's regular communication platform, Webex. After a joint introduction from both D5-1 and D5-2 project leaders, participants were split into two groups (according to any preference they had stated previously for one or other topic, and thereafter randomly); the first focused on discussions related to D5-1, and the second on discussions related to D5-2. A Miro board was prepared for each group to facilitate interactive discussion around a set of questions. The two groups then met back together afterwards to share key points from both discussions and discuss how the project will proceed going forward. Miro was chosen as an ideal visual platform for participants to interact.

One issue with visual methods, including the use of Miro boards, is that those who first place information and answers on them may inadvertently lead other participants' answers. However, this is an issue with all workshop research that involves multiple stakeholders participating simultaneously and indeed the process of the co-production of responses is of interest in itself, since it indicates how stakeholders might work together in real life to co-produce solutions. Since the project is intended to investigate and trial participatory approaches to natural capital valuation, the technique was perfectly suited to our needs.

Questions posed were broad and high level to reflect and elicit what we suspected would be a wide range of responses and opinions from the diverse group of stakeholders invited. Topics were approached within the questions using open, non-leading language, and double-barrelled questions were avoided, to ensure clarity for participants and authenticity within their responses.

Miro boards remained open for two weeks after the workshop to allow any participants who were unable to make it on the day to contribute (in practice only one additional individual contributed outside of the timings of the workshop). After this point the boards were closed for analysis to begin.

Participants have been informed that their contributions will not be identifiable within research outputs, and as such, participant names were pseudonymized prior to analysis. Since we are seeking to identify and report broad narrative themes rather than individual stories and opinions this level of

pseudonymization was felt to be sufficient, however, if at any point quotations or identifiable stories are to be included in future research outputs, these will be achieved by tagging participants with a pseudonymized code.

The Miro boards themselves, workshop transcripts and MS Teams chats were imported into Nvivo for analysis. An organisational node structure was created deductively in the first instance, based on the questions asked across both breakout rooms, and thereafter sub-nodes were created inductively to highlight the qualitative themes revealed through the workshop. The primary node structure is reflected in the sub-headings found in our 'Results' and 'Discussion' sections below, while our sub-nodes are discussed as key themes within these sub-headings.

Structure of report

The report will begin by describing the activities undertaken by each group and how participants were identified. It will move on to consider the results within four key areas which are relevant to both projects, but which will be described here from the perspective of the D5-1 research theme. These areas will then be further considered within the discussion section wherein knowledge gaps will be identified. The report will then consider limitations of the research process, opportunities for future research and next steps for the D5-1 project, before closing with conclusions.

Description of Activities

Plenary session

After an introduction of all the participants a brief explanation of the overarching goal of the two projects and the objectives of the workshop was presented.

Mike Rivington, PI of the JHI D5_2 project, described how climate change impacts on natural capital can be modelled in a spatial context. He emphasised that the approach considered integrates existing research capabilities from a range of different models, but also develops a risk and opportunity assessment framework (ROAF), which draws on information from literature and expert knowledge to understand what the impacts of climate change on natural capital assets will likely be. It was emphasised that the D5-2 breakout group activities were designed to depict a preliminary idea of elements of risk and risk perceptions according to the stakeholders and that the research team will use the data gathered to place the ROAF in a social context, understand how people perceive climate change risks to natural capital and develop better ways to communicate around risks. To explain the importance of communicating risk Mike Rivington highlighted how operating in climate change context means working in a range of uncertainties. Showing a slide containing information on how warmer, wetter or drier Scotland may be in the future, he emphasized that although there might be more water available than before throughout the whole year, a localised analysis looking at the distribution of changes shows very different impacts in precipitation and temperature.

Following this presentation, Simone Martino introduced the project JHI D5_1 emphasizing the objectives and goal of the workshop. He emphasized the overarching goal of the project, to bring in

participatory approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation by considering the importance of social aspects and in general terms of social benefits that can be generated by engaging with different stakeholders and communities. The rationale for operating in this way can be found in different Scottish policies in particular, the Land Use Strategy (Scottish Government, 2021) and the Scotland Forestry Strategy (Scottish Government, 2019). A summary of key objectives was proposed, from the understanding of how we can integrate participatory approaches in natural capital valuation, to the use of different tools that could facilitate the elicitation of values not always clearly emerging through traditional valuation techniques. These might include, for instance, combining a series of analytical tools, deliberative techniques, digital multi scale spatial and 3D models, participatory GIS and virtual reality, that can be used to facilitate stakeholder participation, analyse scenario planning and ultimately inform policy and decision making.

Within this context of value elicitation of forest/ woodland assets, with special focus on Scotland, Simone Martino introduced the goal of the D5-1 breakout session as an opportunity for discussion among experts with the aim of revealing emerging elements or knowledge gaps on forest values and valuation that have not yet been greatly emphasised in research or practice.

Simone Martino introduced the use of the Miro board while Katy Joyce redirected stakeholders to their allocated breakout rooms.

D5-1: Breakout session on forest values and valuation

Eight external stakeholders made part of the breakout session in forest valuation along with four members of the JHI D5_1 project. The institutions represented were: *Scottish government, Scottish Forestry, Forestry and Land Scotland, Nature Scot, Scottish Rural Action, South of Scotland Enterprise, and Scottish Wildlife Trust*. Simone Martino and Katy Joyce from Hutton facilitated the session. The breakout session started with the explanation of the four overarching questions that the research team decided to discuss.

Participants were asked to open a link to a Miro board (circulated in advance). The board contained a square divided into four quadrants (see Appendix II). Each quadrant represented one of four overarching questions relating to natural capital valuation in forests:

Q1: What do you value about forests?

Q2: Why do you value forests in this way?

Q3: How might climate change affect the value of forest-based natural capital?

Q4: What opportunities exist for improving valuation of natural capital to support the resilience of forests?

Participants were asked to create virtual post-it notes within the Miro platform with their answers written in brief and to drop them onto the correct quadrant. Questions were asked and responded to one at a time, with participants being given roughly five minutes to add their answers to the board and then roughly ten minutes to discuss in the group; Simone and Katy used some prompts questions to stimulate the debate (see Appendix III) before moving on to the next question.

D5-2

The second session of the workshop explored experts' risk perceptions with regards to the effects of climate change on natural capital, with a particular focus on drought, flood and wildfire risk. The results showed that participants had strong perceptions of risk in relation to droughts, flooding and wildfires, as well as increasing temperatures (which was brought up unprompted as a significant risk), and felt that these risks were highly likely, highly severe, and urgent. In response to these risks, participants thought there was need for diversification of land use, financial incentives, regulation and implementation of nature-based solutions, in order to mitigate and manage their effects. Overall, greater collaboration and integration of land management across sectors were considered necessary to enable these responses. Participants also emphasised the importance of research for evidence, and of communication with decision-makers and the general public. Details are provided in a separate report (Poskitt et al., 2023).

Moving back to the main room

The workshop continued with a summary of the ideas discussed in two breakout rooms. Sam Poskitt reported on the discussion emerged in the breakout room about climate change risk perception and mitigating actions. Sam mentioned that many topics on climate change risk were brought up although there was no time to explore them all. The risk to natural capital was considered severe and this is already evident. People got stuck into thinking about how we can respond to the existing threats of natural capital. Some major ideas were proposed such as improvement in soil management, carbon storage, water storage, and in general terms it was suggested that there was a need to manage land in a more joined up way. For details on the discussion about climate change risk on natural capital it is possible to read Poskitt et al. (2023).

Simone Martino proposed a summary of the second group discussing values in the forestry and woodland context. It was quickly proposed that beyond the more evident provisioning and regulating services, cultural services such a sense of place and community emerged very strongly, and that this aspect is not yet sufficiently emphasised in decision making. In terms of motivations to valuing, it emerged that this can be linked to personal experience, but also to the way in which we manage our assets building on a utilitarian perspective of life. Climate change is considered to have contrasting effects, from increase in timber volume and higher timber demand to reduction in those contexts where climate change can facilitate the spread of pests and diseases. It was mentioned that we need to produce a better modelling of climate change and in some way to create scenarios to better understand how natural capital can respond to events such as flood risk and drought, to mention a few. What emerged was the idea that under these climate change scenarios we can restructure the way in which we manage forest in order to take into account values of biodiversity and to balance timber productivity with biodiversity and forest resilience.

Identification of Participants

As the workshop was designed to gather the views of expert stakeholders, individual contacts and specific organisations relevant to the topic area were proposed by the D5-1 and D5-2 Project and Work Package Leads based on their own knowledge of natural capital stakeholder networks. A snowball approach was taken thereafter based on participants' own suggestions for other relevant

contacts. Due to significant project links to Scottish Government participants approached were primarily based in Scotland with a few others based in England to represent stakeholder types not covered in Scotland (natural capital finance, etc).

Results

This section describes the results of the questions raised in the D5-1 breakout group.

Natural Capital Values

A broad range of types of natural capital values and ecosystem services emerged from stakeholder responses in the first quadrant on the top left of the board, which requested expressions of what people value about forests (as a commercial element) and woodlands.

Q1: 'What do you value about forests?'

- **Biodiversity Values**

A number of stakeholders valued forest natural capital for its facility to provide benefits to support biodiversity. This included the provision of habitats, corridors / connecting habitats, shelter and water sources for multiple species of wildlife. At the centre of what was valued about natural capital from this perspective was the wildlife and biodiversity itself.

- **Regulatory Values**

Some valued forest natural capital for its ability to provide regulatory services. Commonly cited regulating services were production of fresh air / oxygen, carbon sequestration, flood mitigation, maintaining and improving water quality and local climate regulation, such as the provision of cooling / shade and heat island reduction. Some supporting services were cited too, such as soil stability, soil regeneration and creation of mycelium network. One individual valued forest natural capital's regulatory capacity for contributing to policy-related goals, in particular Scotland's climate change targets.

- **Provisioning Values**

Provisioning values also featured, such as the provision of food and biofuel. The most highly mentioned were grazing land and timber, the latter being mentioned more than once.

- **Economic Values**

Leading on from provisioning values, a few stakeholders described the economic values they associated with forest natural capital. They noted it's facility for producing income from timber production, which might boost incomes for organisations and / or for the economy more generally.

- **Cultural Values**

- **Forests are a partial solution to the biodiversity and climate change crises**

Forest natural capital was seen by some as part of the solution to the biodiversity and climate change crises and thus protecting biodiversity and habitats was considered important. The IPBES Values Assessment was quoted by one participant to reinforce their reasons for valuing forest natural capital in this way. Nature loss and climate change were noted as increasing in significance in recent years.

- **There is a need for regulatory ecosystem services that forests provide**

One participant noted that as a professional, the regulatory services forests provide are of value in spaces beyond the forest itself.

- **Industry pressure sometimes influences the way forests are valued**

Several participants highlighted that the timber industry influences how they value forests and forest natural capital. This is related to industry timber production quotas, and regulations placed on industry around timber sustainability and climate change mitigation. As a result, certain types of timber, or forest natural capital, are valued more highly than others and this in turn influences the values of other stakeholders. One participant saw this as a cycle, wherein income from timber production could be reinvested into more sustainable forest management.

- **Forests support the economy**

The contribution of forests to the economy was highlighted by two participants, while one acknowledged that the forest 'pays my wages'.

- **Forests are important to communities**

A number of participants described how communities need forests to provide cultural services. They provide community space, a sense of place, visual stimulation, access to cultural / historic heritage and archaeological features, and a link to people's personal experiences of forests. As such the availability of access to forests is seen as a factor that influences the types and levels of value communities and individuals place upon them. More broadly, as one participant wrote, 'people like woodlands and forests'.

- **Professional interests can influence how forests are valued**

Several participants highlighted that their professional interest in and knowledge of forests influenced the way they valued them. One person described their work as highlighting the 'invisible values' of forests and the importance of these, while another stated that some of their values were led by policy. Another suggested that perhaps some forest values exist simply because professional opinion and practice holds them to be true within a particular framework of values which one must fit into as a professional, and therefore that these values are perpetuated: 'I mean, do you value forests because you value them, or because you were told that there's something valuable about them?'. However, it was also highlighted that the forest sector is aware that a broader range of types of values, particularly those that are unquantifiable, need to be brought to the fore.

- **Personal preferences can influence how forests are valued**

At the same time, some participants highlighted the fact that their reasons for valuing forests in the way they do are personal. This may be related to their personal experiences, connections and

Participants also suggested a number of opportunities that might result from climate change. These included an increased demand for sustainable timber and increase in length of growing season leading to higher timber incomes. Risks to forests may conversely lead to people valuing them more highly and recognising them as an important climate change solution and natural flood management solution.

- **Chains of impact**

It is recognised that the impact to the forest ecosystem can have multiple cascade consequences. For example, the impact to the timber sector may have negative repercussions in the supply chain for the entirety of commercial forestry. However, from an ecological perspective the entire forest ecosystem can suffer from reductions in ability to support biodiversity, and that in turn can generate lower condition of forest and a diminished sensory experience for visitors to forests.

- **Balance of risks and opportunities**

One participant suggested that forest values may in fact remain the same and noted that for people who did not spend much time in forests, they may not notice any difference.

- **Perceptions of risk**

Beyond an evidenced map of risk that is supported by modelling approaches, risk perceptions can vary considerably. This is reflected by individuals' capacity to interact with the environment. Relational aspects of forests can be more tangibly perceived to be at risk, however, cultural and recreational services that are not elicited by those who do not engage either physically or spiritually with forest ecosystems, may not be perceived differently under climate change.

- **Other effects of risks in valuation**

The perception that climate risk will reduce forest condition and then its value, opposes the idea that certain values may increase due to a new recognition of the essential role that forests have in counteracting the effects of climate change. Therefore, it is recognised from this perspective that there is a positive option value, or a capacity to use forest services in the future because of the benefits generated by limiting climate change.

Figure 3 provides a snapshot of the discussion around how climate change affects the value of forest-based natural capital.

Figure 3: ideas on the impact of climate change in forest valuation dimensions and process

Responses to Risk: Opportunities for Improving Valuation

The last discussion was directed to explore opportunities for improving valuation of natural capital to support the resilience of forests. As a prompt for stimulating the discussion, thoughts were sought which aired any aspect not yet considered in the workshop, any other difficulties in valuing forest, or any kind of opportunities in this specific arena. Under this theme participants responded to the final quadrant at the bottom right of the Miro board.

Q4: 'What opportunities exist for improving valuation of natural capital to support the resilience of forests?'

- **Opportunities for improving data, measurement and understanding**

Themes that emerged included need for improved data collection, measurement and modelling around forest ecosystem service benefits, and improved understanding of the full range of benefits and risks forests provide, both within forests and woodlands and off-site (for example through modelling a more accurate measurement of natural flood management, or better understanding of linkages between above and below ground carbon). It was felt that fuller understanding of these aspects would aid in setting appropriate values.

- **Opportunities for improving community participation**

Community consultation and co-design of forest management emerged as a strong theme due to its capacity for increasing understanding around the range of context-specific values held by local communities around forests and woodlands and their changing landscapes, which explore aspects

such as felt connections and sense of place and which should be incorporated into valuations. Tied to this it was suggested that improved valuation of cultural heritage would be helpful.

- **Opportunities for including other capitals**

Explicit incorporation of other types of capitals in valuation (such as human and social capital, for example) was thought to be helpful, to allow for the forging of links with a wellbeing economy, and to aid in understanding community values 'through these lenses'.

- **Opportunities for balancing economic versus alternate values**

The importance of finding ways to value these different aspects of forests and woodlands was emphasised by participants who noted the need for sustainability and other wider benefits of forests to be weighed up against their economic benefits. This knowledge could be used to facilitate the seeking of funding streams (with the potential in particular for blending public and private finances) and human resources for forest protection / adaptation to enable climate change mitigation / adaptation and increase biodiversity, and specifically for investing in creating future ready forests through the diversification of woodland type / species mix in woodland creation / restocking in order to increase resilience in forests.

Figure 4 provides a snapshot of the ideas proposed.

Figure 4: suggestions for future opportunities in the area of forest valuation

Discussion

The results highlight a number of key points for discussion.

Responses to questions 1 & 2 reveal, interestingly, that personal and cultural values were highlighted as strongly as economic values and values related to provisioning and regulating services (which might be expected to emerge from experts acting in professional capacity). For some stakeholders, this personal perspective stems from a strong sense of connection to forest, such as feeling in tune with their surroundings when spending time in woodlands, particularly for those who have had the opportunity to grow up next to woodland. For others, values proposed are motivated by professional and economic interests relevant to the entire country (Scotland) and to, for example creation of jobs, and which spill over to several economic sectors. There is a consensus on a dichotomic approach in valuing forest reflecting personal values placed on it, but also the necessity to operate in an economic system that poses specific boundaries. Thus, the way in which some values are elicited are not necessarily aligned to how people would like to manifest the importance that they could place on forests but influenced and forced by the context. It is necessary to use a range of approaches and tools to disentangle this dichotomy and highlight the disproportionate influence of professional knowledge and media in the formation of preferences. The current lack of technical and conceptual capacity in this area urgently needs to be addressed.

It was evident from the discussion however that economic forest values are not disconnected from presenting partial solutions to the climate and biodiversity crises in themselves: for example, timber income can be reinvested in sustainable forest management and the traditional timber industry reconfigured to generate multiple forest services such as biodiversity, aesthetic values, and a sense of community. Further answers proposed that reasons to value forest facilitate the emergence of values to reflect a new way of living that in turn feeds into a deceleration of pace of life and contributes to achieving economic degrowth (but not in terms of wellbeing). These points suggest that natural capital values should somehow reflect a rethinking of conceptions of wealth which includes both economic value and wellbeing values, ideas which echo current Scottish Policy thinking within the National Performance Framework (<https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/>) and beyond ('Towards a robust, resilient wellbeing economy for Scotland', Scottish Government, 2020)

Further influence on our way of expressing values may come from external factors. Communication of research seems to have a certain influence such as the last IPBES report on the methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature. In addition, it is recognised that valuation can be reinforced by feedback loop; it emerged that working in the woodland/forest sector is a specific choice made by people who give high value to them. However, professional operations facilitate knowledge exchange and learning about all the different works that other people in forest-related sectors do, influencing the way forest is valued. In addition, the strong propensity to utilitarianism that human beings have developed has skewed valuation approaches and methodological formulation of tools and methods towards the analysis of benefits that can be quantified in monetary units, while more implicit values that cannot be commensurate, if not in a qualitative way, require a discussion to generate consensus in group or in community conversation. This highlights how design of tools for valuing natural capital must be carefully configured to take into account a range of views and influences which feed into each other dynamically.

Research in valuing nature has certainly had an influence on policy which has a greater propensity to propose more ambitious and diverse perspectives around managing land than those dictated by perspectives focused purely on improving economic exchange values. For some stakeholders valuing

forest is led by a policy focus, for instance related to the Regional Land Use Partnership, around the exploration of cultural heritage as well as historical and archaeological features, elements so far neglected by efforts to compile data and information. Ideas emerging in valuing forest are shaped by the different policy context. In the 1980s and 1990s there was an emerging attention in forestry to biodiversity and community landscaping. This has now changed into a focus on climate change and biodiversity and nature loss. This consideration anticipates the next step towards the discussion on forest values centred on the idea that climate change has an influence on them, and that managing and investing in forest conservation can be revisited according to the uncertainty of climate change impacts. Natural capital valuation can feed into these discussions and should be designed accordingly to provide the information required for informed and inclusive decision-making.

The uncertainty around climate change and the impact on forest condition and provisioning of ecosystem services is reflected in several contrasting ideas reflecting on the one hand the increase in growth rate in timber volume as a vector of additional income, carbon sequestration and increase in demand for sustainable building material, and on the other side the likely reduction in timber values caused by the spread of pests and diseases (on site impacts), limitation in the ability to support biodiversity functional processes, or the capacity to provide services such as water regulation because of more extreme flood events (that generate off-site impacts). Additional damage to the forest ecosystem can be foreseen in some areas where high wildfire risk intensity is expected to happen. Natural capital valuation tools need to be designed so they are capable of reflecting the dynamic changes expected due to climate change.

Some interesting perspectives refer to the real capacity that we have to perceive changes in values under climate change; while certain tangible aspects of forests can be affected in a visible and quantifiable way, such as change in timber provision and reduced regulating capacity especially in those cases where a threshold effect is reached (tipping point), it is suggested that perhaps other cultural and recreational services that are not benefited by these particular services or which do not have a direct relationship with forests, may not be impacted under climate change. Higher values may be placed upon forests under climate change if their role in mitigating climate change risk is recognised, while better connections with forests may improve message delivery around the gravity of climate change. Natural capital valuation tools must be capable of measuring both decreases and increases in value, but assumptions should not be made that all values will be different under climate change conditions.

Nevertheless it is expected that climate change will likely alter the option value, or the use value of future services if these are expected to be affected by climate change. This may lead to repercussions around the way investors would like to invest in forest and land restoration and rewilding as a result, based on their changing perceptions and understandings of climate change. However, looking at the patterns of carbon credits purchased as offsetting mechanisms through woodland creation, it seems that investors are not thinking far enough ahead but leave land and forest managers to manage natural assets in a way that provides carbon credits or offsets carbon use. The goal for some participants, however, is to create future ready places and future ready forests which are adapted to climate change and build in species diversification. This is a strategy for the commercial sector but also for public uses of forest, to be implemented in regional land use plans as a crucial output ensuring that what will be planted in the coming years and in the short term is going to be adapted to the climate in 2050 / 2060 to build more resilient forests and woodlands. Consideration of the interactions between natural capital valuation and carbon credit schemes will be a point of interest moving forwards.

The discussion touched also on the fact that there is the opportunity to make a step forward-in financing adaptation of forest to climate change. There is pressure from the timber industry and the Scottish Government to decide what forests can deliver against climate change targets. Thus, one of the targets is the amount of sustainable timber brought to market that obviously may help to reduce plastics and embody carbon. To achieve this, it is necessary to invest in forest adaptation and species diversification today, making the right decisions now for forests that will come to fruition 50 years in the future. Setting the right valuation mechanisms will be vital in ensuring these decisions are based on the fullest and most accurate information.

This involves not only the creation of new forest that requires the right space (a decision that can conflict with other land uses), but also deciding when and how we restock forests that have been felled, to ensure that they are future ready. This investment strategy is about balancing timber productivity with the resilience of forests for future ready places. There is inevitably a trade-off required in any given strategy, but it is necessary to move towards greater diversity by selecting the right species for the right places because following the current model of managing timber may result in some species failing to reach maturity at all under changing environmental conditions. Again, dynamic and accurate natural capital tools and mechanisms will be capable of guiding decision-making in this area.

Continuing the discussion on trade-offs in the decision of forest management, it emerged that conflicts between forest industry strategy and local community interests have already emerged in the South of Scotland. In some areas where community concerns were noted, there was evidence of a rapidly changing landscape. Extensive areas of woodlands were created over the last 5-6 years, with local communities not necessarily feeling empowered to have any say in the decision-making process. From this discussion it emerged that participatory community engagement can play a critical role in ensuring valuations take into account the multiple relational values of a wide range of stakeholder perspectives.

Opportunities for Future Research: Knowledge Gaps Highlighted

This section explores knowledge gaps explicitly recognised by participants during the workshop.

There is a need to understand:

- the knowledge gap around values for communities and individuals related to sense of place, cultural heritage, historic / archaeological features – lack information / data evidence – currently underestimated which often means local community values are not taken into account;
- how to increase perceptions of the importance of financing and resourcing forest adaptation over the economic benefits of timber creation (especially single species timber) / default afforestation (which can cause maladaptation), and industry preferences for these courses of action, and to consider how natural capital valuation can support this;
- how to shift investor focus from carbon offsetting to what's best for the forest / climate change adaptation / future ready forests / species diversification etc to ensure investment goes to the right places, and to consider how natural capital valuation can support this;

- how to balance investment into sustainability and adaptation of UK forest natural capital with the fact that we import timber from overseas from places that may not be as sustainable, and to consider how natural capital valuation can support this; and
- how to deal with over-dependency on species such as Sitka Spruce in Scotland and to consider how natural capital valuation can support this.

This section considers knowledge gaps highlighted implicitly throughout the workshop.

There is a need to understand:

- the dichotomy or duality of personal and professional values held in forests / woodlands, which highlights a knowledge gap around how to integrate the two within natural capital valuation and how to weight items against each other within this;
- the impact / influence of the timber industry on natural capital values, to consider if it is necessary to find ways to reduce this influence and if so, how this could be done;
- to what extent policy impacts / influences what is valued within forests and therefore what is valued within natural capital valuations, whether greater influence should or should not be sought and if so, how this could be achieved;
- how to improve understanding of the full range of benefits and risks forest natural capital provides, both within forests and woodlands and off-site;
- how to account for 'unquantifiable' aspects of forest natural capital value;
- whether the values that are assigned to forest natural capital implicitly are fit for purpose - are we valuing certain things about forests because we are told to value them?;
- the range of potential negative and positive impacts of climate change on forest natural capital and related impacts for commercial forestry, the timber industry, the building sector, for forest visitors and for other stakeholders;
- how to improve data collection, measurement and modelling around forest ecosystem service benefits;
- how to improve channels for community engagement in natural capital valuation through participatory consultation / co-designed projects to ensure values assigned are context specific and take into account local needs and feelings;
- how to explicitly incorporate consideration of human, social and productive capitals in the valuation of natural capital and to consider how these aspects can link into policy ideas related to a wellbeing economy; and
- how to weigh up economic values against other types of values in order to ensure a more even balance of funding to allow it to address forest protection, adaptation and mitigation strategies, biodiversity loss and greater resilience within forests.

Limitations of the Workshop

As with all qualitative research data gathered is context specific to the participants and different answers may have been gathered if a different set of participants had been involved. In particular, a number of policy and community group stakeholders were invited to the workshop but did not

attend and therefore the balance was skewed almost exclusively to practitioner viewpoints. Future research aims to engage a wider range of stakeholders through a set of two more workshops to gather a wider range of viewpoints.

As the team was new to using Microsoft Teams some technical issues inevitably arose which sadly led to the loss of one participant from the workshop. An in-person workshop may have enabled the gathering of richer data although the use of the Miro board meant that more reticent participants were able to add their thoughts, knowledge and experience without being expected to speak up. Later workshops are expected to be held in-person to address this issue.

A major limitation noted by participants in feedback after the workshop was the broad nature of the questions, which led to some participants feeling frustrated that their specific interests were not able to be addressed. Since knowledge within the academic community on the topic of natural capital valuation and how to make it work in practice is still relatively in its infancy, moving beyond this level of questioning in the first instance would have caused us to miss a set of basic knowledge gaps that vitally need to be addressed. Future work can build upon this data to hone in on more specific areas of valuation pertinent to particular groups of stakeholders. Indeed, this workshop marks the start of a longer-term engagement with stakeholders throughout which there will be opportunities for more granular discussions.

Next Steps

The results of this workshop will be merged with a preliminary analysis of the valuation methods used in valuing forests, with specific reference to the Scottish context, to summarise gaps in values and valuation methods and address the formulation of a framework able to tackle any issues that have emerged from the gap analysis. A further set of workshops with stakeholders will inform this framework by exploring scenario development under a range of climate change and policy conditions. Implementation of the valuation framework will be carried out at landscape scale in areas yet to be decided. According to the relevance of case study areas to stakeholders, more consideration and granular perspectives not captured in this workshop will have the opportunity to emerge, contributing to the further development of ideas around the need for exploring new values in a longer-term engagement.

Conclusions

In the concluding part of the workshop, the participants and Hutton research team specified how to make good use of the information gathered. In particular it was proposed that the ideas which emerged should be integrated with information previously extracted from the academic literature that spans natural capitals, and approaches used in the forest context, to specific uses of participatory approaches in valuation and influences of the natural capital concept in policy.

It was suggested that we are at the beginning of a new process in which we are trying to understand the relationships between people and natural capital and the impacts of climate change on valuation, not just within this project but across the strategic research program funded by the Scottish Government. Therefore, we decided to start from a simple basic position, that can stem initiatives to develop a more detailed discussion which over the course of the remaining four years

will generate more in-depth conversations with the same stakeholders and a broader range of key players such as forest and land managers that were not present at this workshop.

Ultimately, it was proposed that the workshop will be key to summarising gaps in research and practice around valuing forest and forest natural capital in the Scottish context in order to design a related natural capital valuation framework to be validated with a broader range of stakeholders including landowners, land managers and politicians. It was finally suggested that to follow on with the ideas which emerged in this workshop, the research group will organise future engagement activities based on in-person events exploring development scenarios for landscapes and specific natural assets informed by climate change projections and various policy contexts for several case studies still under discussion.

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Appendix I: Consent Form

RESEARCH CONSENT FORM FOR WORKSHOPS WITH FARMERS, LAND / FOREST OWNERS / MANAGERS, AND INSTITUTIONAL STAKEHOLDERS

Title of Project:	Bringing in Participatory Approaches to Widen the Scope of Natural Capital Valuation / Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital (Earth, Water and Fire) – Joint Project Workshop
Principal Investigator:	Investigator: Katy Joyce (Hutton), Co-investigators: Simone Martino (Hutton) Maria Nijnik (Hutton), Mike Rivington (Hutton)
Study Number:	These Projects have received funding from the Scottish Government’s Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS) funding programme 2022-2027.

Please Initial Box

1. I confirm that I have read, or someone else has read to me, and I understand, the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and these have been answered fully and explicitly.	
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary, and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without providing any reason and without my legal rights being affected.	
3. I understand that although the James Hutton Institute will pseudonymise all data that may identify me personally, it may be that the institution you work for might be identifiable. There is a small risk that due to your position in your organisation, comments or information shared may be traceable back to you. We will make every effort to limit this effect.	
4. I understand that I will have the opportunity to review the analysis of anonymised or pseudonymised data (i.e., data that do not identify me personally, but which may identify the organisation that I work for, and which may be identified by a key code) before finalisation of the research outputs and I will be given the opportunity to withdraw my consent at this stage. I understand that this data cannot be withdrawn once research outputs are finalised.	
5. I understand that the study is being conducted by researchers of the James Hutton Institute (“Hutton”, Scotland) and that the research is funded by the Scottish Government’s Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS)	

<p>6. I understand that confidentiality will be maintained at all times, and it will not be possible to connect any choices, statements or opinions to me and my organisation in any publications/outputs unless I have given my permission for this.</p>	
<p>7. I agree to take part in the workshop. I understand that I will be asked to participate in focus group discussions and other activities to be carried out in plenary meeting to help us understand:</p> <p>1) the natural capital resources on your land, what values you attribute to them, what processes you use to value them and how climate change may be impacting on their value now and in the future; if, and how, natural capital approaches are currently used on your land and why; and how we can best work with stakeholders to share best-practice around natural capital valuations and approaches;</p> <p>2) your perceptions of wildfire risk to natural capital on your land arising from climate change in Scotland; and your thoughts on what might influence you to manage wildfire risk differently / more sustainably; and your thoughts on how landowners, communities and institutional stakeholders could work together to reduce wildfire risk.</p>	
<p>8. I agree for the workshop to be audio recorded, for transcription purposes only for the two projects Bringing in Participatory Approaches to Widen the Scope of Natural Capital Valuation / Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital (Earth, Water and Fire)</p>	
<p>9. I understand that notes will be taken during the discussion without connecting ideas, opinion and facts to specific stakeholders.</p>	
<p>10. I understand that any information disclosed within the workshop must remain confidential to the workshop group and I will not share this information outside the workshop, unless I have the relevant person's expressed permission.</p>	
<p>11. I understand that I will receive no compensation for my participation. The information acquired during the workshop will not be used by any member of the project team for commercial purposes. Therefore, I cannot expect any royalties or payments from the research project in the future.</p>	
<p>12. I give permission for audio/video recording taken during the workshop where I may be identifiable to be used for publicity and dissemination purposes of this project.</p>	
<p>13. I understand that if I do not give permission, images of me seen in the video recording will be edited (e.g. blurred faces) so that I will not be identifiable.</p>	
<p>14. I acknowledge that I have read and understood the privacy notice (see below) and I understand how my personal data will be used in this study.</p>	
<p>15. I understand that the outputs of this research will be circulated in the form of reports, scientific papers, briefings, podcast, blog posts and other content for the websites of the Bringing in Participatory Approaches to Widen the Scope of Natural Capital Valuation / Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital (Earth, Water and Fire) projects.</p>	
<p>16. I give permission for the data that I provide in the workshop to be deposited in pseudonymised form in a publicly accessible data archive or repository so it can be used for future research and learning.</p>	

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Name of Participant (please print) Signature Date

PI/Researcher Name (please print) Signature Date

Privacy Notice

The James Hutton Institute (“Hutton”, “us” or “we”) will use your personal data for the purposes of the joint research undertaken in the Bringing in Participatory Approaches to Widen the Scope of Natural Capital Valuation / Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital (Earth, Water and Fire) projects. Our legal basis for processing your data is that it is necessary for our research tasks which we carry out in the public interest. You can ask us to delete or stop processing your data prior to the finalisation of the research outputs by contacting katy.joyce@hutton.ac.uk or simone.martino@hutton.ac.uk and you will be given the opportunity to review the use of your data in the research prior to finalisation. In this event, we will stop the processing as soon as we can, and to the extent this is within our control. However, this will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before your withdrawal of consent.

We are the Data Controller of your personal data collected in this study. Your personal data shall be retained only for as long as it is necessary for the purposes of the project (2027) and shall be anonymised and stored afterwards, without any possibility to link your choices, statements or opinions to your name. Only the anonymous or pseudonymous datasets shall be used for statistical elaboration and to produce results to be communicated and disseminated.

You have rights in relation to your personal data. Please see our Privacy Notice at www.hutton.ac.uk/terms for further information or contact our Data Protection Officer on dpo@hutton.ac.uk, or by telephone at 01382 346814.

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Appendix II Instructions circulated before the workshop for using Miro during the JHI Natural Capital workshop

Introduction

Hello, and thank you for joining the James Hutton Institute for this expert consultation workshop, which aims to:

- (1) gather expert insights into the valuation of forest-based natural capital (the natural resources that enable the benefits and services people depend upon and benefit from) in Scotland, and how this may be affected by climate change;
- (2) explore perceptions of risk related to potential flood, drought and wildfire as a result of climate change.

The workshop will be held online, via Microsoft Teams, and will include some interactive activities using an online collaboration tool called Miro. For these activities, we will be splitting into two parallel sessions. One session will concentrate on Objective 1 (valuation of natural capital), and the other will concentrate on Objective 2 (risks related to climate change). You will have freedom to choose which session you prefer to join, and we will have time to review and discuss both sessions in plenary at the end.

What activities will we conduct, using Miro?

To explore Objective 1, we will ask you to contribute your views by adding virtual 'sticky notes' to a pre-prepared matrix. Each segment of the matrix will have a different question related to valuation of forest-based natural capital in Scotland.

To explore Objective 2, we will ask you to contribute your views about potential risks to natural capital, associated with climate change, by adding virtual 'sticky notes' to a pre-prepared matrix. The matrix will display 'likelihood of risk' on the vertical axis and 'severity of risk' on the horizontal axis. We would like you to position your sticky notes on the matrix, according to whether you think they

are: 'low likelihood, low severity', 'high likelihood, low severity', 'low likelihood, high severity', and 'high likelihood, high severity'.

Instructions for using Miro.

What follows is a set of instructions for using Miro, as well as a link to a practice 'Miro board' with two, simple practice questions. Please do try to look through these, if you get chance before the workshop, as they will help you to engage with the workshop activities, even if you have used Miro before.

1. Please access the practice Miro board by following this link:
https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMXD8EIA=?share_link_id=406447846838
2. Navigate around the board by pressing and holding the **right click** button on your mouse, or if using a laptop, pressing the **bottom right corner** of your mousepad and holding whilst you move your finger around the pad.
3. Zoom in and out by using the **scroller** on your mouse, or if using a laptop, by holding **two fingers** on the mousepad and sliding them up and down.
4. Please add your responses to each of the practice questions in the pre-prepared matrix, using the 'sticky notes' function. To do this, click on the small square on the toolbar on the left of the screen, as shown:

Select whatever colour stick note you like and then click on the area of the board where you want your sticky note to appear:

D5-1 Joint Natural Capital Workshop with D5-2.

Then, type your response to the practice question into the sticky note, click on an area of the board outside the sticky note, and your response will appear on the board:

You can edit your sticky note(s) at any time by clicking on it, typing to edit the text, or using the white toolbar that appears below the sticky note to change the colour, text size, and font, or clicking on the white dots around the edge of the sticky note to change its size.

Appendix III: Questions prepared for stimulating conversation

D5-1 Session

The Miro board was divided in 4 quadrants, each proposing a question. Before collecting data, it was communicated that each person could answer either generally or according to personally experience in the context and geographic area where she operates.

Q1: What do you value about forests? 	
Q3: How might climate change affect the value of forest-based natural capital? 	

Questions for stimulating conversation about Q1: What do you value about forests? (15-20 mins)

- Begin by asking all participants the open question: “What do you value about forests?” and encourage them to note their ideas on post-its in Miro.
- Make it clear that we want to explore a wide range of aspects and different types of value, so participants should focus on what is most important to them.
- To elicit a range of responses, the facilitator can ask:
 - Is there anything else that you value about forests?
 - Are there any different types of value that haven’t been noted yet?
- The facilitators will look at and briefly comment on the values proposed by stakeholders according to their knowledge and experience of forests and of the current policy and management framework (Q1). They will then move on to a set of questions exploring the topics proposed in the other quadrants. NOTE: We can prioritise these questions, to ensure we manage to discuss the most important points within the time available.

Questions for stimulating conversation about Q2: Why do you value forests in this way? (15-20 mins)

- Begin by asking all participants the open question: “Why do you value forests in this way?” and encourage them to note their ideas on post-its in Miro.
- If needed, further prompts can include:
 - What types of value do you consider important in the way you value forests?
 - What influences the way you value forests?
 - How might other people value forests differently to you?
- For reference, we hope this question will help us to elicit information on:

- A) whether participants' reasons for valuing forests in particular ways are based on economic, wellbeing, health, spiritual, cultural, biodiversity, ecosystem services provision, for themselves, for the communities they serve, or for their organisations
- B) Whether there are particular factors which influence their conceptions of valuation: (I.e. from media, landowners, industry, availability of certain tools and techniques, their financial circumstances, etc).

Questions for stimulating conversation on Q3: How might climate change affect the value of forest-based natural capital? (15-20 mins)

- Begin by asking all participants the open question: "How might climate change affect the value of forest-based natural capital?" and encourage them to note their ideas on post-its in Miro.
- If needed, follow-on questions can include:
 - What aspects that you value about forests are affected by climate change?
 - Which aspects of the climate do you perceive are changing?
 - How do you think these changes are affecting the aspects of forests that you value?
 - How do/might the effects of these changes influence the value of the aspects you value about forests?
 - What are the threats and opportunities created by changes in climate for forests?
 - Please tell us about any responses/options/strategies you think could protect forests from threats and maximise opportunities.

Questions for stimulating conversation about Q4: What opportunities exist for improving valuation of natural capital to support the resilience of forests? (15-20 mins)

- Begin by asking all participants the open question: "What opportunities exist for improving valuation of natural capital to support the resilience of forests?" and encourage them to note their ideas on post-its in Miro.
- If needed, follow-on questions can include:
 - Are there any aspects of forests that you do not value? If so, why not?
 - Are there any aspects of forests you think are important, that are not formally valued? Why?
 - What are the main difficulties involved in valuation of forests? (Formally or informally)

